

1 **Interleaved Binomial kT-Points for**
2 **Water-Selective Imaging at 7T**

3 Daniel Löwen¹, Eberhard D. Pracht¹, Rüdiger Stirnberg¹,
 Patrick Liebig² and Tony Stöcker^{1,3}

4 ¹*German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases (DZNE), Bonn, Germany*

5 ²*Siemens Healthcare GmbH, Erlangen, Germany*

6 ³*Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Bonn, Germany*

7 **Words (Body):** 2798

8 **Keywords:** ultra-high field MRI, parallel transmission (pTx), k_T-points, water
9 excitation

10 **Corresponding author**

11 Tony Stöcker
12 Deutsches Zentrum fuer Neurodegenerative Erkrankungen e.V. (DZNE)
13 Venusberg-Campus 1/99
14 53127 Bonn
15 Germany
16 Tel: +49 228 43302-860
17 E-Mail: tony.stoecker@dzne.de

18 Submitted to Magnetic Resonance in Medicine as a Technical Note

19 **Abstract**

20 **Purpose**

21 We present a time-efficient water-selective, parallel transmit RF excitation pulse
22 design for ultra-high field applications.

23 **Methods**

24 The proposed pulse design method achieves flip angle homogenization at ultra-
25 high fields by employing spatially non-selective k_T -points pulses. In order to
26 introduce water-selection, the concept of binomial pulses is applied. Due to the
27 composite nature of k_T -points, the pulse can be split into multiple binomial
28 sub-pulse blocks shorter than half the precession period of fat, that are played
29 out successively. Additional fat precession turns, that would otherwise impair
30 the spectral response, can thus be avoided. Bloch simulations of the proposed
31 interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses were carried out and compared in terms of
32 duration, homogeneity, fat suppression and pulse energy. For validation, *in vivo*
33 MP-RAGE and 3D-EPI data were acquired.

34 **Results**

35 Simulation results show that interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses achieve
36 shorter total pulse durations, improved flip angle homogeneity and more robust
37 fat suppression compared to available methods. Interleaved binomial k_T -points
38 can be customized by changing the number of k_T -points, the sub-pulse duration
39 and the order of the binomial pulse. Using shorter sub-pulses, the number of
40 k_T -points can be increased and hence better homogeneity is achieved, while
41 still maintaining short total pulse durations. Flip angle homogenization and fat
42 suppression of interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses is demonstrated *in vivo* at

43 7T, confirming Bloch simulation results.

44 **Conclusion**

45 In this work, we present a time efficient and robust parallel transmission technique
46 for non-selective water excitation with simultaneous flip angle homogenization
47 at ultra-high field.

48 Introduction

49 Increased static magnetic fields enhance the signal to noise ratio in MRI, allowing
50 to acquire images with higher resolution or to reduce the acquisition time
51 [1]. However, a problem emerging at ultra-high fields ($B_0 \geq 7\text{T}$) are B_1^+
52 inhomogeneities due to radio-frequency (RF) interferences [2, 3, 4] and dielectric
53 resonances [5]. Different solutions have been proposed to counteract the problems
54 associated with B_1^+ inhomogeneities: Adiabatic pulses [6, 7], dielectric pads [8],
55 dedicated coil designs [9, 10] and parallel transmission (pTx) [11, 12]. Parallel
56 transmission has turned out to be particularly effective for subject specific and
57 subject independent B_1^+ adjustments [13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. RF shimming solely
58 sets fixed optimized amplitude and phase combinations on each transmitting
59 channel to reach improved homogenization of the B_1^+ distribution [18]. pTx
60 instead aims at a homogeneous flip angle distribution by transmitting different
61 RF wave forms on each channel, while gradient pulses are applied to cover
62 a certain transmit k-space trajectory [19]. However, combining pTx with fat
63 suppression poses additional challenges at ultra-high fields.

64 In sequences with a low phase encoding bandwidth such as echo planar imaging
65 (EPI) signal from fat appears displaced along the phase encoding direction. As a
66 result of the chemical shift, severe image artifacts occur in the brain demanding
67 for elimination of fat signal. But standard fat suppression methods require long
68 durations or produce high SAR, particularly at ultra-high fields.

69 A single rectangular RF-pulse with a specific duration (RECT pulses) [20] offers
70 a low-SAR, time efficient solution to eliminate fat signal. In the small tip angle
71 approximation, the spectral response of a rectangular pulse is given by a sinc
72 function and water excitation can be achieved by adjusting the roots of the
73 sinc function to the resonance frequency of fat. A drawback of this method is

74 the fixed duration of the pulse and the limitation to B_1^+ shimming, which in
75 many instances does not provide sufficient degrees of freedom to homogenize the
76 B_1^+ -field across the entire brain [18].

77 It has been proposed to combine RECT pulses with k_T -points [21], which deposit
78 energy at discrete points in transmit k-space, to use the full potential of pTx
79 [22]. k_T -points consist of a limited number of rectangular excitation sub-pulses
80 interleaved with gradient blips to travel between transmission points. The
81 drawback of combining pTx homogenization and RECT pulses are increased
82 pulse durations and therefore limited echo and/or repetition times of fast imaging
83 sequences. At 7T each sub-pulse has to have a duration of ~ 1 ms, leading to a
84 long total pulse duration. This method will be referred to as RECT k_T -points
85 in this work.

86 Another method proposed by Malik et al. is water excitation using binomial pulses
87 [23] with optimized binomial coefficients, where each RF-pulse is separately B_1^+ -
88 shimmed [24]. This method leads to shorter pulse durations, but no excitation
89 k-space trajectory is involved.

90 Therefore, we propose interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses to achieve high image
91 homogeneity and spectral selection while maintaining short RF-pulse durations.
92 The basic approach is similar to the work described in [24] but extended to pTx
93 pulses, leveraging the full potential of multichannel transmission.

94 **Methods**

95 **Pulse design**

96 All pulses were calculated and optimized in the small tip angle approximation
97 using the Siemens pTx PulseDesign (PPD) framework (Siemens Healthcare,

108 Erlangen, Germany) implemented in Matlab R2012b (Mathworks, Natick, MA).
109 For all pulse calculations the standard B_0 and B_1^+ scanner calibration data was
110 used.

111 Image homogenization was achieved by employing spatially non-selective k_T -
112 points pulses [21], and water-selection was introduced by applying the concept
113 of binomial pulses [23]. In this work, k_T -points were located at the highest
114 contributions of the inverse Fourier transform of the Bloch simulation of a
115 RF-shimmed pulse, similarly to [21], where the mask was taken into account.
116 However, more elaborate methods can be applied to find k_T -point locations.

117 A straightforward approach, to create binomial pulses, is to repeat the k_T -points
118 pulse when fat and water protons are out of phase, tipping the fat magnetization
119 back to the longitudinal axis, see Figure 1(b). In this case, the excitation k-space
120 trajectory is the same as for a single pulse, but is repeated several times from
121 beginning to end. However, if the total pulse length is longer than half the
122 precession period of fat ($T_{fat}/2$), the second pulse has to be applied at an odd
123 multiple of $T_{fat}/2$, leading to long pulse durations and significantly increased
124 B_0 sensitivity as the spectral response is compressed accordingly. At 7T, $T_{fat}/2$
125 is only approximately $510\mu s$ such that a spacing of $3T_{fat}/2$ or $5T_{fat}/2$ may be
126 required to accommodate sufficient k_T -points sub-pulses. These will be referred
127 to as standard binomial k_T -points pulses.

128 Due to the composite nature of k_T -points, the pulse can be split into sub-pulse
129 blocks shorter than $T_{fat}/2$: The first sub-pulse block is repeated directly after
130 $T_{fat}/2$, immediately followed by the second sub-pulse block played out in the
131 same way, and so forth (Figure 1(c)). As a consequence, the excitation k-space
132 trajectory is not traversed from beginning to the end in the same fashion as
133 it would be in a single non-water-selective pulse. Instead, the first point in

124 k-space is visited again after a few sub-pulses, to apply the second RF pulse
125 at this position precisely after $T_{fat}/2$. Using this method, B_0 sensitivity is not
126 increased, as the first root of the spectral response of the binomial pulse is always
127 at the resonance frequency of fat. This proposed method will be referred to as
128 interleaved binomial k_T -points.

129 A python implementation of the proposed method can be found at [https://](https://github.com/mrphysics-bonn/interleaved_binomial_kTpoints)
130 github.com/mrphysics-bonn/interleaved_binomial_kTpoints.

131 For comparison, the RECT k_T -points method was implemented [20, 22]. Each
132 sub-pulse duration was adjusted to minimize the excitation of fat ($\sim 1\text{ms}$ at 7T),
133 see Figure 1(a).

134 Simulations

135 Pulse optimizations and Bloch simulations were performed based on B_0 and B_1^+
136 maps of a gel phantom without considering relaxation effects.

137 First, interleaved binomial k_T -points (Figure 1(c)) were compared to standard
138 binomial k_T -points (Figure 1(b)) with regards to time efficiency. Both pulse
139 types (standard and interleaved pulses) were simulated for different sub-pulse
140 durations (10 to $180\mu\text{s}$) and for different binomial orders (1-1 and 1-2-1) at 7T
141 ($T_{fat}/2 \sim 510\mu\text{s}$). The resulting total pulse duration was compared for 5 and 7
142 k_T -points. A maximal sub-pulse duration of $180\mu\text{s}$ was used, because longer
143 sub-pulse durations would have resulted in blocks of one sub-pulse each.

144 Additionally, Bloch simulations of the interleaved binomial k_T -points pulse were
145 carried out and compared to the RECT k_T -points pulse in terms of duration,
146 homogeneity, fat suppression quality and pulse energy. In order to compare the
147 fat suppression quality, the B_0 map was shifted to the fat frequency simulating

148 a “fat-only” phantom. The influence of different numbers of k_T -points (5 and 7),
149 different binomial orders (1-1 and 1-2-1) and different sub-pulse durations were
150 investigated.

151 Experiments

152 In addition to the Bloch simulations, the performance of different pulses was
153 compared for a gel phantom and *in vivo* using an MP-RAGE sequence [25] as
154 well as 3D-EPI [26]. The MP-RAGE sequence utilizes a standard adiabatic
155 inversion pulse in CP-mode (circular polarization) and both sequences use pTx
156 excitation pulses for the gradient echo train.

157 For comparison of the homogenization quality, a CP-mode based $100\mu\text{s}$ rect-
158 angular pulse, a RECT pulse with 3 k_T -points (1.02ms sub-pulse durations)
159 and two different interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses (5 k_T -points with $100\mu\text{s}$
160 sub-pulses binomial 1-1 and 7 k_T -points $50\mu\text{s}$ sub-pulses binomial 1-1 pulses)
161 were used with a nominal flip angle of 8° in the gradient echo train of the
162 MP-RAGE sequence. Using these pulses and the corresponding B_0 and B_1^+
163 maps of the subject, Bloch simulations were performed to estimate the flip angle
164 distribution in the brain.

165 Finally, the fat suppression quality was also compared *in vivo* using the 3D-
166 EPI sequence with representative whole-brain fMRI settings. Excitation types
167 included a RECT pulse with 3 k_T -points, two different interleaved binomial k_T -
168 points pulses (5 k_T -points with $100\mu\text{s}$ sub-pulses binomial 1-1 and 1-2-1 pulses)
169 and a single CP-mode based $100\mu\text{s}$ rectangular pulse (no fat suppression).

170 The imaging parameters of the MP-RAGE sequence were: TI = 1100 ms,
171 TE/TR: 5.1 / 2500 ms, turbofactor 176, 1mm^3 isotropic resolution, readout
172 pixel bandwidth = 110Hz. The sequence utilizes an optimized linear reordering

173 scheme with elliptical scanning and 2D parallel imaging (a $2 \times 2_{z_1}$ CAIPIRINHA
174 sampling with a CAIPI shift of 1 in secondary phase encode direction was used)
175 [27, 28]. The total scan time was 2:23 min.

176 3D-EPI imaging parameters were: TE = 20 ms, TR = 2.2 s, 1.5mm^3 isotropic
177 resolution, readout pixel bandwidth = 1754Hz, sagittal slice orientation, pos-
178 teroanterior primary phase encoding direction. A $3 \times 2_{z_1}$ blipped-CAIPI sampling
179 was used [29].

180 The pulse design was implemented on a MAGNETOM 7T Plus scanner (Siemens
181 Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany) using a head array coil with 32 receive and 8
182 transmit channels (Nova Medical, Wilmington, USA). For the *in vivo* measure-
183 ments, the pulse calculation was performed online during the actual imaging
184 session. *In vivo* experiments were performed in accordance with guidelines set by
185 the institutional review board and prior, written informed consent was obtained
186 from the subjects.

187 Results

188 Simulations

189 Figure 2 shows the total pulse duration for the standard and interleaved binomial
190 k_T -points pulses, plotted against the total duration of the corresponding, non-
191 binomial k_T -points pulses (not water-selective). Binomial 1-1 or 1-2-1 k_T -points
192 pulses are at least twice or three times as long, respectively. A corresponding
193 line with slope 2 and 3 represents optimal time efficiency, disregarding water-
194 selectivity. The time is used most efficiently when the second (and third)
195 application of the pulse is started directly after finishing the previous application
196 without dead time. Therefore, the RF segments of the binomial water excitation,

197 as defined in Fig. 1, should have a duration of $T_{fat}/2$ to use time most efficiently.
 198 Figure 2 demonstrates that, if the duration of the RF segment exceeds $T_{fat}/2$,
 199 the standard binomial 1-1 water excitation gains T_{fat} in duration, while the
 200 interleaved binomial 1-1 water excitation only gains $T_{fat}/2$ in duration. The
 201 same applies to binomial 1-2-1 water excitation, where exceeding $T_{fat}/2$ with
 202 the single pulse adds 2 times T_{fat} in duration in the standard case and 2 times
 203 $T_{fat}/2$ for interleaved binomial water excitation. The most time efficient versions
 204 of the interleaved pulses, marked by red circles, are achieved with the longest
 205 possible sub-pulse durations, for a certain number of blocks.

206 Simulation results for a few selected example pulses are listed in Table 1. In
 207 order to get a good compromise between water-selection and homogenization for
 208 the RECT water excitation, the number of k_T -points was chosen to be 3, as in
 209 [22], resulting in a total pulse duration of 3.29ms. Then, interleaved binomial
 210 k_T -points pulses with sub-pulse durations leading to the highest time efficiency
 211 (red circles in Fig. 2) and a basic sub-pulse duration ($50\mu\text{s}$) were chosen. The
 212 shortest total durations (1.86ms and 1.87ms) could be achieved with a small
 213 number of k_T -points and binomial 1-1 water excitation. However, with short
 214 sub-pulses and therefore increased RF-amplitudes the pulse energy rises, leading
 215 to potential SAR problems. Using the proposed interleaved binomial k_T -points
 216 1-1 pulses, the mean fat flip angle increases only slightly compared to the RECT
 217 k_T -points pulse, while water is excited more homogeneously (cf. Table 1). By
 218 applying interleaved binomial k_T -points 1-2-1 pulses, the mean fat flip angle
 219 considerably decreased compared to the RECT k_T -points pulse or binomial 1-1
 220 water excitation.

221 Experiments

222 The improved flip angle homogeneity of interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses
223 was examined *in vivo* and is shown in Fig. 3. Corresponding Bloch simulation
224 results using the B_0 and B_1^+ calibration data confirm that homogeneity increases
225 with the number of k_T -points. The histograms of the Bloch simulations present
226 the flip angle distribution over the brain (the brain outline is drawn in the images
227 with blue), which gets narrower with increasing number of k_T -points. Improved
228 flip angle homogeneity when using more k_T -points is also observed *in vivo*, using
229 MP-RAGE imaging, especially in the cerebellum. In CP mode, very low signal
230 is measured in the cerebellum and the flip angle drops almost down to zero
231 in some voxels. The 3 k_T -points RECT pulse noticeably improves the image
232 homogeneity throughout the brain compared to CP mode excitation, but still
233 lacks intensity in the lower part of the brain. Interleaved binomial k_T -points (5
234 or 7 points) achieve better homogeneity than the RECT pulse (3 points) while
235 still having shorter durations.

236 A comparison regarding the fat suppression quality for a typical fMRI time series
237 acquisition using 3D-EPI is shown in Figure 4. Although the interleaved binomial
238 1-1 pulse and the RECT k_T -points pulse eliminate most of the fat signal, minor
239 fat artifacts are still present with reduced intensity due to B_0 inhomogeneities (see
240 red arrows in Figure 4). When using interleaved binomial 1-2-1 water excitation,
241 which are less sensitive to B_0 inhomogeneities, fat artifacts are mostly suppressed.
242 Two additional subjects were measured with the same setup to demonstrate the
243 robustness of the method and are shown in Supporting Information Figure S1.
244 Both subjects show increased homogeneity with increasing number of k_T -points
245 and subject 2 shows improved water excitation quality. Whereas subject 3 has
246 already small fat signal without water excitation such that binomial 1-1 and
247 RECT pulses remove the fat signal from the images.

248 Discussion

249 In this work, we proposed a time efficient combination of flip angle homogeniza-
250 tion and water excitation for ultra-high field applications. Interleaved binomial
251 k_T -points provide an opportunity to circumvent potential weaknesses of binomial
252 pulses when repeating a long pulse after an odd multiple of $T_{fat}/2$. The com-
253 posite nature of k_T -points is utilized to split the pulse in blocks, which are then
254 reassembled to improve the time efficiency and the fat suppression robustness. In
255 most cases interleaved binomial k_T -points use time more efficiently compared to
256 the standard version, leading to fewer dead times, where no RF or gradient pulses
257 are applied. Even in cases in which time is not used more efficiently (cf. Figure
258 2), interleaved binomial k_T -points are more favorable due to the insensitivity to
259 off-resonance effects. Standard binomial pulses produce a sinusoidal excitation
260 profile, which is compressed when prolonging the delay between the RF segments,
261 leading to a reduced bandwidth of the minimum. The fat resonance on the
262 other hand is relatively broad [30], especially in presence of B_0 inhomogeneities,
263 so that fat is not completely suppressed when the spectral excitation profile is
264 compressed. In contrast, interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses are designed such,
265 that the first root of their spectral response always matches the fat resonance
266 frequency.

267 Another advantage of interleaved binomial k_T -points, in contrast to the RECT
268 k_T -points method [20, 22], are two additional degrees of freedom in the pulse
269 design process. For example, one can add more k_T -points and at the same time
270 reduce sub-pulse durations to maintain the same total pulse durations. However,
271 SAR rises in this case. The number of k_T -points is constrained for RECT pulses,
272 because each additional point adds about 1ms (at 7T) to the pulse duration,
273 which restricts the homogenization quality. Therefore the proposed interleaved

274 binomial k_T -points were able to reduce the water flip angle inhomogeneity (up
275 to 40% lower) compared to RECT k_T -points [22] and simultaneously achieve
276 shorter pulse durations by 43%, but at the expense of over seven-fold increased
277 pulse-energies compared to the very low energy of RECT pulses. The highlighted
278 values in Table 1 show, that interleaved binomial k_T -points can achieve different
279 goals and a compromise between different parameters can be found depending
280 on individual demands. Binomial 1-1 pulses achieve the shortest durations and
281 can be used if fast RF-pulses are needed. The best fat suppression is achieved
282 by the binomial 1-2-1 pulse, because it has the broadest bandwidth of the
283 nulling frequency and therefore is less sensitive to B_0 inhomogeneities. Although
284 each sub-pulse block has to be repeated three times, still shorter durations are
285 achieved compared to the RECT pulses. Optimizing the binomial coefficients at
286 water and fat frequencies, as suggested in [24], could provide further improved
287 robustness against B_0 inhomogeneities.

288 Since the k_T -points pulse is optimized prior to rearranging into binomial water-
289 excitation, universal k_T -points pulses [16] can be simply converted into universal
290 interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses. However, because the pulse gets longer
291 by rearranging the homogenization performance deteriorates for 1-1 and even
292 more for binomial 1-2-1 pulses and B_0 inhomogeneities make more impact. This
293 issue could be addressed by optimizing the pulse after (or simultaneously with)
294 determining the k-space trajectory.

295 Whether interleaved binomial k_T -points still provide an advantage compared to
296 RECT pulses at even higher static fields ($>7T$), where the duration of RECT
297 sub-pulses decreases (to $\sim 760\mu s$ at 9.4T or $\sim 610\mu s$ at 11.7T [31, 32]), remains to
298 be shown. Furthermore, SAR rises at higher static fields, which could constrain
299 the sub-pulse duration of interleaved binomial pulses such that RECT pulses

300 become more favorable.

301 Since every RF-pulse and every gradient blip can be described as a rotation of
302 the Bloch vector and rotations are not commutative in general, changing the
303 order of sub-pulses could lead to losses in performance at high flip angles. For
304 small tip angles however, the rotations can be regarded as commutative, because
305 the longitudinal magnetization is considered constant. As binomial pulses rely
306 on the small tip angle approximation [23, 33], interleaved binomial k_T -points
307 are efficient only for small flip angle applications such as segmented 3D-EPI
308 [34] or FLASH [35]. For the 3D-EPI sequence, as used for fMRI, interleaved
309 binomial k_T -points provide the mandatory fat suppression as well as flip angle
310 homogenization at ultra-high fields.

311 Conclusion

312 We have shown that interleaved binomial k_T -points provide a flexible method to
313 achieve homogeneous whole-brain water-selective small tip angle excitations at
314 7T. A tradeoff regarding flip angle homogeneity, off-resonance robustness and
315 pulse duration can be found by varying the sub-pulse duration, the number of
316 k_T -points and the binomial order.

317 The proposed method presents time-efficient, water-selective, parallel transmit
318 RF excitation pulses for ultra-high field applications. The properties of k_T -points
319 are combined with binomial pulses to achieve short, B_1^+ and B_0 insensitive water
320 excitation pulses.

321 **Acknowledgments**

322 Thanks to Robin Heidemann, Rene Gumbrecht, and Raphael Tomi-Tricot from
323 Siemens for their assistance. This work received financial support from the
324 European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant
325 agreement 885876 (AROMA) and through the German Federal Ministry of
326 Education and Research (BMBF; funding code 01ED2109A) as part of the SCAI-
327 FIELD project under the aegis of the EU Joint Programme - Neurodegenerative
328 Disease Research (JPND) (www.jpnd.eu).

329 References

- 330 [1] M. E. Ladd, P. Bachert, M. Meyerspeer, E. Moser, A. M. Nagel, D. G.
331 Norris, S. Schmitter, O. Speck, S. Straub, and M. Zaiss, “Pros and cons of
332 ultra-high-field MRI/MRS for human application,” pp. 1–50, dec 2018.
- 333 [2] D. I. Hoult and D. Phil, “Sensitivity and power deposition in a high-field
334 imaging experiment,” *J. Magn. Reson. Imaging*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 46–67,
335 2000.
- 336 [3] T. S. Ibrahim, R. Lee, A. M. Abduljalil, B. A. Baertlein, and
337 P. L. Robitaille, “Dielectric resonances and B1 field inhomogeneity in
338 UHFMRI: computational analysis and experimental findings,” *Magn.*
339 *Reson. Imag.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 219–226, 2001. [Online]. Available:
340 <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11358660>
- 341 [4] C. M. Deniz, “Parallel Transmission for Ultrahigh Field MRI,” pp. 159–171,
342 jun 2019.
- 343 [5] Q. X. Yang, J. Wang, X. Zhang, C. M. Collins, M. B. Smith, H. Liu, X. H.
344 Zhu, J. T. Vaughan, K. Ugurbil, and W. Chen, “Analysis of wave behavior
345 in lossy dielectric samples at high field,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 47, no. 5,
346 pp. 982–989, 2002.
- 347 [6] R. A. De Graaf and K. Nicolay, “Adiabatic rf pulses: Applications to in
348 vivo NMR,” *Concepts Magn. Reson.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 247–268, 1997.
- 349 [7] D. G. Norris, “Adiabatic radiofrequency pulse forms in biomedical nuclear
350 magnetic resonance,” *Concepts Magn. Reson. Part B Magn. Reson. Eng.*,
351 vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 89–101, 2002.

- 352 [8] Q. X. Yang, W. Mao, J. Wang, M. B. Smith, H. Lei, X. Zhang, K. Ugurbil,
353 and W. Chen, “Manipulation of image intensity distribution at 7.0 T:
354 Passive RF shimming and focusing with dielectric materials,” *J. Magn.*
355 *Reson. Imaging*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 197–202, 2006.
- 356 [9] J. T. Vaughan, H. P. Hetherington, J. Otu, J. W. Pan, and G. M. Pohost,
357 “High Frequency Volume Coils,” *Spectroscopy*, vol. C, pp. 206–218, 1994.
- 358 [10] D. C. Alsop, T. J. Connick, and G. Mizsei, “A spiral volume coil for improved
359 rf field homogeneity at high static magnetic field strength,” *Magn. Reson.*
360 *Med.*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 49–54, 1998.
- 361 [11] U. Katscher, P. Börnert, C. Leussler, and J. S. Van den Brink, “Transmit
362 SENSE,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 144–150, 2003.
- 363 [12] Y. Zhu, “Parallel Excitation with an Array of Transmit Coils,” *Magn. Reson.*
364 *Med.*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 775–784, 2004.
- 365 [13] P. Ullmann, S. Junge, M. Wick, F. Seifert, W. Ruhm, and J. Hennig,
366 “Experimental analysis of parallel excitation using dedicated coil setups and
367 simultaneous RF transmission on multiple channels,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*,
368 vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 994–1001, 2005.
- 369 [14] K. Setsompop, L. L. Wald, V. Alagappan, B. Gagoski, F. Hebrank,
370 U. Fontius, F. Schmitt, and E. Adalsteinsson, “Parallel RF transmission
371 with eight channels at 3 Tesla,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp.
372 1163–1171, 2006.
- 373 [15] W. Grissom, C. Y. Yip, Z. Zhang, V. A. Stenger, J. A. Fessler, and D. C.
374 Noll, “Spatial domain method for the design of RF pulses in multicoil
375 parallel excitation,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 620–629, 2006.

- 376 [16] V. Gras, A. Vignaud, A. Amadon, D. Le Bihan, and N. Boulant, “Universal
377 pulses: A new concept for calibration-free parallel transmission,” *Magn.*
378 *Reson. Med.*, vol. 77, no. 2, pp. 635–643, 2017.
- 379 [17] J. Herrler, P. Liebig, R. Gumbrecht, D. Ritter, S. Schmitter, A. Maier,
380 M. Schmidt, M. Uder, A. Doerfler, and A. M. Nagel, “Fast online-customized
381 (FOCUS) parallel transmission pulses: A combination of universal pulses
382 and individual optimization,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, no. February 2020, pp.
383 1–14.
- 384 [18] W. Mao, M. B. Smith, and C. M. Collins, “Exploring the limits of RF
385 shimming for high-field MRI of the human head,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*,
386 vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 918–922, 2006.
- 387 [19] J. Pauly, D. Nishimura, and A. Macovski, “A k-Space Analysis of Small-
388 Tip-Angle Excitation,” *J. Magn. Reson.*, vol. 81, pp. 43–56, 1989.
- 389 [20] R. Stirnberg, D. Brenner, T. Stöcker, and N. J. Shah, “Rapid fat suppression
390 for three-dimensional echo planar imaging with minimized specific absorption
391 rate,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 76, no. 5, pp. 1517–1523, 2016.
- 392 [21] M. A. Cloos, N. Boulant, M. Luong, G. Ferrand, E. Giacomini, D. Le Bihan,
393 and A. Amadon, “K T-points: Short three-dimensional tailored RF pulses
394 for flip-angle homogenization over an extended volume,” *Magn. Reson. Med.*,
395 vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 72–80, 2012.
- 396 [22] C. Le Ster, A. Moreno, F. Mauconduit, V. Gras, R. Stirnberg, B. A.
397 Poser, A. Vignaud, E. Eger, S. Dehaene, F. Meyniel, and N. Boulant,
398 “Comparison of SMS-EPI and 3D-EPI at 7T in an fMRI localizer study
399 with matched spatiotemporal resolution and homogenized excitation

- 400 profiles,” *PLoS One*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 1–17, 2019. [Online]. Available:
401 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0225286>
- 402 [23] P. J. Hore, “A New Method for Water Suppression in the Proton NMR
403 Spectra of Aqueous Solutions,” pp. 539–542, 1983.
- 404 [24] S. J. Malik, D. J. Larkman, D. P. O’regan, and J. V. Hajnal, “Subject-
405 specific water-selective imaging using parallel transmission,” *Magn. Reson.*
406 *Med.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 988–997, 2010.
- 407 [25] J. P. Mugler and J. R. Brookeman, “Three-dimensional magnetization-
408 prepared rapid gradient-echo imaging (3D MP RAGE),” *Magn. Reson.*
409 *Med.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 152–157, 1990.
- 410 [26] R. Stirnberg and T. Stöcker, “Segmented K-space blipped-controlled aliasing
411 in parallel imaging for high spatiotemporal resolution EPI,” *Magn. Reson.*
412 *Med.*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 1540–1551, 2021.
- 413 [27] F. A. Breuer, M. Blaimer, M. F. Mueller, N. Seiberlich, R. M. Heidemann,
414 M. A. Griswold, and P. M. Jakob, “Controlled aliasing in volumetric parallel
415 imaging (2D CAIPIRINHA),” *Magn. Reson. Med.*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 549–
416 556, 2006.
- 417 [28] D. Brenner, R. Stirnberg, E. D. Pracht, and T. Stöcker, “Two-
418 dimensional accelerated MP-RAGE imaging with flexible linear reordering.”
419 *MAGMA*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 455–62, oct 2014. [Online]. Available:
420 <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24510154>
- 421 [29] K. Setsompop, B. A. Gagoski, J. R. Polimeni, T. Witzel, V. J. Wedeen, and
422 L. L. Wald, “Blipped-controlled aliasing in parallel imaging for simultaneous

- 423 multislice echo planar imaging with reduced g-factor penalty,” *Magn. Reson.*
424 *Med.*, vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 1210–1224, 2012.
- 425 [30] M. A. Bernstein, K. F. King, and X. J. Zhou, *Handbook of MRI pulse*
426 *sequences*, 2004.
- 427 [31] R. Stirnberg, D. Brenner, T. Stöcker, and N. J. Shah, “A Simple Fat
428 Suppression Method for Accelerated and Low-SAR 3D-EPI,” vol. 21,
429 p. 80, 2013. [Online]. Available: [http://submissions.miracd.com/ismrm2013/
430 proceedings/files/0080.PDF](http://submissions.miracd.com/ismrm2013/proceedings/files/0080.PDF)
- 431 [32] R. Stirnberg, D. Pflugfelder, T. Stöcker, and N. J. Shah, “High-Resolution
432 3D-fMRI at 9.4 Tesla with Intrinsically Minimised Geometric Distortions,”
433 *Proc. ISMRM*, vol. 21, p. 2372, 2013.
- 434 [33] D. Thomasson, D. Purdy, and J. P. Finn, “Phase-modulated binomial RF
435 pulses for fast spectrally-selective musculoskeletal imaging,” *Magn. Reson.*
436 *Med.*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 563–568, 1996.
- 437 [34] B. A. Poser, P. J. Koopmans, T. Witzel, L. L. Wald, and
438 M. Barth, “Three dimensional echo-planar imaging at 7 Tesla,”
439 *Neuroimage*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 261–266, 2010. [Online]. Available:
440 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2010.01.108>
- 441 [35] A. Haase, J. Frahm, D. Matthaei, W. Hanicke, and K. D. Merboldt, “FLASH
442 imaging. Rapid NMR imaging using low flip-angle pulses,” *J. Magn. Reson.*,
443 vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 258–266, 1986.

Design-Parameters			Resulting parameters			
Type	Number of k_T -points	Sub-pulse duration [ms]	Total duration [ms]	Water FA rmsd [deg]	Fat FA mean [deg]	Pulse energy [mJ]
RECT	3	1.02	3.29	1.51	0.20	2.6
B 1-1	5	0.1	1.87	1.37	0.17	12.1
B 1-1	5	0.05	1.62	1.34	0.17	25.9
B 1-1	7	0.1	2.72	0.98	0.20	11.3
B 1-1	7	0.05	1.86	0.90	0.15	20.4
B 1-2-1	5	0.1	1.89	1.45	0.02	9.2
B 1-2-1	7	0.05	2.88	1.02	0.02	15.5

Table 1: Simulation results of different water-selective pulses. The mean flip angles (FA) were calculated from Bloch simulations based on B_0 and B_1^+ maps of a gel phantom. Type "RECT" is a simple rectangular k_T -points water excitation pulse [20, 22]. "B" is the proposed interleaved binomial k_T -points pulse. Remaining excitation inhomogeneity is indicated by the root-mean-squared deviation from the mean (rmsd). The highlighted parameters are the optimal results from this set of pulses.

Figure 1: A comparison of different water excitation pulse schemes. (a) RECT 3 k_T -points water excitation (as used in [22]). (b) "Standard" binomial 1-1 excitation applied to a 5 k_T -points pulse. The pulse is repeated at an odd multiple of $T_{fat}/2$. (c) Proposed interleaved version of the binomial 1-1 5 k_T -points pulse. The pulse is split in two sub-pulse blocks, each shorter than $T_{fat}/2$. A1-5 and B1-5 denote the 5 sub-pulses of the two binomial k_T -points pulses. The blue bars indicate coherent RF segments.

Figure 2: Total pulse duration of standard and interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses plotted against the duration of the corresponding non-binomial k_T -points (not water-selective) pulse for (a) 5 and (b) 7 k_T -points. The optimal time efficiency line has a slope of 2 for binomial 1-1 (upper plots) and a slope of 3 for binomial 1-2-1 water excitation (lower plots). Red circles indicate pulses, whose total duration is closest to the optimal case and time is used most efficiently for the interleaved versions. All interleaved binomial k_T -points pulses have the same pulse bandwidth (first root of spectral response at fat frequency) as opposed to almost all standard binomial k_T -points pulses.

Figure 3: *In vivo* MP-RAGE acquisition with different excitation pulses (CP binomial 1-1 / $3k_T(1020\mu s)$ RECT / $5k_T(100\mu s)$ interleaved binomial 1-1 / $7k_T(50\mu s)$ interleaved binomial 1-1) and respective Bloch simulations. A brain mask (blue line) was extracted from MP-RAGE images and applied to the simulated flip angle maps for histogram generation.

Figure 4: *In vivo* 3D-EPI acquisition with different excitation pulses. Top to bottom: CP mode without fat suppression (No WE), $3k_T$ RECT pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial 1-1 pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial 1-2-1 pulse. Red arrows indicate remaining fat artifacts.

444 **List of Figures**

445 1 A comparison of different water excitation pulse schemes. (a)
 446 RECT 3 k_T -points water excitation (as used in [22]). (b) "Stan-
 447 dard" binomial 1-1 excitation applied to a 5 k_T -points pulse. The
 448 pulse is repeated at an odd multiple of $T_{fat}/2$. (c) Proposed in-
 449 terleaved version of the binomial 1-1 5 k_T -points pulse. The pulse
 450 is split in two sub-pulse blocks, each shorter than $T_{fat}/2$. A1-5
 451 and B1-5 denote the 5 sub-pulses of the two binomial k_T -points
 452 pulses. The blue bars indicate coherent RF segments. 22

453 2 Total pulse duration of standard and interleaved binomial k_T -
 454 points pulses plotted against the duration of the corresponding
 455 non-binomial k_T -points (not water-selective) pulse for (a) 5 and
 456 (b) 7 k_T -points. The optimal time efficiency line has a slope of
 457 2 for binomial 1-1 (upper plots) and a slope of 3 for binomial
 458 1-2-1 water excitation (lower plots). Red circles indicate pulses,
 459 whose total duration is closest to the optimal case and time is
 460 used most efficiently for the interleaved versions. All interleaved
 461 binomial k_T -points pulses have the same pulse bandwidth (first
 462 root of spectral response at fat frequency) as opposed to almost
 463 all standard binomial k_T -points pulses. 23

464 3 *In vivo* MP-RAGE acquisition with different excitation pulses
 465 (CP binomial 1-1 / $3k_T(1020\mu s)$ RECT / $5k_T(100\mu s)$ interleaved
 466 binomial 1-1 / $7k_T(50\mu s)$ interleaved binomial 1-1) and respective
 467 bloch simulations. A brain mask (blue line) was extracted from
 468 MP-RAGE images and applied to the simulated flip angle maps
 469 for histogram generation. 24

470	4	<i>In vivo</i> 3D-EPI acquisition with different excitation pulses. Top	
471		to bottom: CP mode without fat suppression (No WE), $3k_T$	
472		RECT pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial 1-1 pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved	
473		binomial 1-2-1 pulse. Red arrows indicate remaining fat artifacts.	25
474	S1	<i>In vivo</i> 3D-EPI acquisitions with different excitation pulses for	
475		two additional subjects. Top to bottom: CP mode without fat	
476		suppression (No WE), $3k_T$ RECT pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial	
477		1-1 pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial 1-2-1 pulse. Red arrows	
478		indicate remaining fat artifacts visible for subject 2. Subject	
479		3 already has little fat signal without water-excitation which	
480		disappears with binomial 1-1 or RECT water excitation.	29

481 **List of Tables**

482 1 Simulation results of different water-selective pulses. The mean
483 flip angles (FA) were calculated from Bloch simulations based on
484 B_0 and B_1^+ maps of a gel phantom. Type "RECT" is a simple
485 rectangular k_T -points water excitation pulse [20, 22]. "B" is
486 the proposed interleaved binomial k_T -points pulse. Remaining
487 excitation inhomogeneity is indicated by the root-mean-squared
488 deviation from the mean (rmsd). The highlighted parameters are
489 the optimal results from this set of pulses. 21

490 **Supporting Information Figure**

Supporting Information Figure S1: *In vivo* 3D-EPI acquisitions with different excitation pulses for two additional subjects. Top to bottom: CP mode without fat suppression (No WE), $3k_T$ RECT pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial 1-1 pulse, $5k_T$ interleaved binomial 1-2-1 pulse. Red arrows indicate remaining fat artifacts visible for subject 2. Subject 3 already has little fat signal without water-excitation which disappears with binomial 1-1 or RECT water excitation.